

The corresponding rate law is

$$-\frac{d[\text{DCT}]}{dt} = k_4 [\text{DCT}][\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = k_4[\text{H}^+] \quad (7)$$

The plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}^+]$ gave a straight line passing through the origin (Fig. not shown).

Detailed mechanism of oxidations of Thr and Met by DCT are similar to chloramine-T oxidations reported elsewhere*.

The observed dielectric effect on the rates of oxidations can be explained by Amis concept⁸, which predicts linearities between $\log k_D$ and $1/D$ with negative slopes for the interaction between two dipoles. The plots of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs % methanol were linear with negative slopes in accordance with this concept.

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Excess Volumes of Binary Solutions of 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane with some Ketones at 313.15 K

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In order to investigate the variation in the thermodynamic properties of binary mixtures resulting from isomeric changes in the configuration of component molecules we have been determining excess functions of isomeric compounds in different solvents^{1,2}. In continuation of the above studies we report here excess volumes of five binary systems consisting of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane with different ketones at 313.15 K over entire mole fraction range for each system.

Experimental

2,2,4-Trimethylpentane, dimethyl ketone, isobutyl methyl ketone, acetylacetone and cyclohexanone (L. R. grade) were used after distillation. Cyclohexane (Merck for synthesis) was used as such. The density and boiling point of the pure liquids compared well with the literature values³. The details of the method adopted have been described elsewhere⁴.

Results and Discussion

Excess volumes per mole (V^E) for the mixtures were calculated using the relation,

$$V^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/d - M_1x_1/d_1 - M_2x_2/d_2 \quad (1)$$

where M_i , x_i and d_i represent the molecular weight, mole fraction and density respectively of the component i ($i = 1, 2$) and d is the density of the solution.

Excess volumes for the studied binary solutions are given in Table I. For the systems 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + dimethyl ketone, + isobutyl methyl ketone, and + acetylacetone the excess volumes are positive and nearly symmetrical throughout the studied mole fraction range (Fig. 1). For the system 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + cyclohexanone the excess volumes are negative. In case of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + cyclohexane system the excess volumes are negligibly small exhibiting sigmoid plot having negative values at 0–0.2 mole fraction of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane and positive values at the remaining mole fraction.

Effect of R (alkyl) group: Excess volumes of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + isobutyl methyl ketone are lower than the system 2,2,4-trimethylpentane + dimethyl ketone. This may be due to the favourable interstitial accommodation of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane within the larger alkyl group of isobutyl ketone in comparison to smaller alkyl group in dimethyl ketone which results in negative contribution

(Table 1 contd.)

Fig. 1. Plots of VE against x_1 of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane for the systems: ($\square$) 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+dimethyl ketone, ($\triangle$) + isobutyl methyl ketone, ($\bullet$) + acetylacetone, (Δ) + cyclohexanone, ($\circ$) + cyclohexane and ($\cdots$) + acetophenone.

TABLE 1—MOLAR EXCESS VOLUMES (VE) FOR BINARY SYSTEM OF SOME KETONES WITH 2,2,4-TRIMETHYLPENTANE AT 313.15 K

x_1	VE (ml mol $^{-1}$)
2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (1) + dimethyl ketone	
0.023 8	0.218
0.054 4	0.266
0.118 9	0.544
0.250 5	0.949
0.363 6	1.162
0.459 6	1.271
0.592 7	1.259
0.757 2	1.023
0.851 5	0.688
2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (1) + isobutyl methyl ketone (2)	
0.083 7	0.137
0.267 2	0.349
0.369 3	0.449
0.460 6	0.532
0.579 5	0.610
0.699 9	0.497
0.808 1	0.488
0.890 1	0.353

2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (1) + acetylacetone (2)	
0.032 8	0.079
0.072 7	0.096
0.152 0	0.119
0.235 1	0.253
0.390 8	0.348
0.446 3	0.498
0.555 0	0.601
0.668 0	0.708
0.916 1	0.147
2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (1) + cyclohexanone (2)	
0.041 8	-0.106
0.092 6	-0.355
0.225 7	-0.459
0.341 3	-0.504
0.562 6	-0.391
0.604 8	-0.363
0.710 0	-0.488
0.897 7	-0.058
2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (1) + cyclohexane (2)	
0.107 8	-0.088
0.233 5	-0.004
0.490 0	+0.001
0.592 6	+0.026
0.789 9	+0.020

towards excess volume as also reported earlier for similar studies for other systems⁵.

Earlier we reported the excess volumes for the system 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+acetophenone², also reproduced here for comparison (Fig. 1). Higher values of excess volumes for these solutions in dimethyl ketone in comparison to that in acetophenone may be due to the predominant hydrogen bond stretching in case of dimethyl ketone than in acetophenone when 2,2,4-trimethylpentane is separately mixed with them.

Effect of keto group: Excess volumes for 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+cyclohexane are negligibly small and exhibit sigmoid plot with respect to mole fraction. But solutions of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane in cyclohexanone show large negative excess volumes over the entire mole fraction range. Negative excess volumes in case of the latter system which consists of non-polar 2,2,4-trimethylpentane and polar cyclohexanone molecules may be due to dipole-induced dipole interaction between unlike component molecules. This type of interaction predominates in a system involving cyclic ketone, viz. cyclohexanone over the normal aliphatic ketone, e.g. dimethyl ketone, which is evident from the lower values of excess volumes for the system 2,2,4-trimethylpentane+cyclohexanone than +dimethyl ketone. The dipole-induced dipole type of interaction seems to be further favoured if the number of keto groups increased in the molecule since there are lower excess volumes for the mixtures containing acetyl acetone (a diketone) in comparison to those which contain dimethyl ketone.

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Ir Spectra of the Oxides and Sulphides of Triarylphosphines and Triarylarisines

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TRIPHENYLPHOSPHINE oxide and trimethylphosphine oxide are the only phosphine oxides for which ir spectral data are available in the literature¹. No data are available for phosphine sulphides, triarylarisine oxides and sulphides, although Merijan and Zingaro² studied the ir spectra of some trialkylarisine oxides.

Experimental

The following compounds were prepared as described in the literature³⁻¹⁸ - phosphine oxides: triphenyl³, m.p. 156-57°, tribenzyl⁴, 213-14°, tri-*o*-tolyl⁵, 152-53°, tri-*m*-tolyl⁶, 110-11°, tri-*p*-tolyl⁶, 145-46°, tri-*o*-anisyl⁷, 216-17°, tri-*p*-anisyl⁶, 142-43°, tri-*m*-chlorophenyl⁸, 135-36°, tri-*p*-chlorophenyl⁸, 177-78°; phosphine sulphides: triphenyl⁹, m.p. 160-61°, tribenzyl⁹, 213-14°, tri-*p*-tolyl⁶, 185-86°, tri-*p*-methoxyphenyl⁶, 113-14°; arsine oxides: triphenyl¹⁰, m.p. 193-94°, tribenzyl¹¹, 219-20°, tri-*o*-tolyl¹², 150-51°, tri-*m*-tolyl¹², 169-70°, tri-*p*-tolyl (monohydrate)¹³, 89-90°, tri-*o*-anisyl¹⁴, 203-204°, tri-*p*-anisyl (monohydrate)¹⁷, 92-93°; arsine sulphides: triphenyl¹⁵, m.p. 161-62°, tribenzyl¹⁶, 212-13°, tri-*m*-tolyl¹², 186-87°, tri-*p*-tolyl¹⁴, 170-71°, tri-*o*-anisyl¹³, 185-86°, tri-*p*-anisyl¹⁸, 108-09°.

Tri-*o*-tolylphosphine sulphide: A solution of tri-*o*-tolyl phosphine (3.7 g) and sulphur (0.4 g) in carbon disulphide (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. Removal of carbon disulphide gave an oily product which solidified on cooling (3.3 g); recrystallisation from methanol afforded crystals, m.p. 159-60°

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(Found: C, 74.9; H, 6.1. C₂₁H₂₁PS calcd. for: C, 75.0; H, 6.3%).

The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 21 double-beam spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

In view of the complexity of the spectra, the bond frequencies were determined by comparing the spectra of the phosphine oxides and arsine oxides with those of the corresponding phosphines and arsines along with those of the corresponding sulphides. The bands due to P→O and As→O stretching are very strong and could easily be identified. The P→S bonds are weaker but there was no difficulty in identifying them. But the As→S bands seemed to be very weak and in most cases they merged with CH out-of-plane deformations of the benzene ring in the 850-750 cm⁻¹ region (arising due to two adjacent free hydrogen atoms and five adjacent free hydrogen atoms)¹⁹. This made the identification of the As→S stretching vibration very difficult and in some cases impossible. So any assignments made will be unreliable. Table I gives the P→O, P→S and As→O frequency assignments made in the present study.

TABLE I—IR STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹)

	ν _{P→O}		ν _{As→O}
(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₃ PO	1182	(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₃ AsO	876
(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ PO	1183	(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ AsO	883
(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1182	(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO	868
(<i>m</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1181	(<i>m</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO	885
(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1179	(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO	884
(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1181	(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO	881
(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1182	(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO	670
(<i>m</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1188		
(<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1187		
	ν _{P→S}		
(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₃ PS	687	(<i>m</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PS	688
(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ PS	689	(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PS	685
(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PS	686	(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PS	689

The P→O and P→S bonds in triarylphosphine oxides and triarylphosphine sulphides are seen to have stretching vibrational frequencies in the range 1188-1179 and 689-685 cm⁻¹, respectively. The frequencies are remarkably constant and substitution in the benzene nuclei does not cause any significant frequency shift. The As→O stretching frequency is in the range 885-870 cm⁻¹.

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